

Modulating lifetime distribution through variable excitation pulse length and power: a case study on colloidal PbS quantum dots

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Abstract: We investigated the laser power-dependent photoluminescence (PL) decay profiles of oleic-acid capped PbS quantum dots (QDs) in toluene, with a mean size of approximately 2.6 nm, under both long duration (LD) and short duration (SD) excitation pulse limits. The absorption cross section (ACS) of PbS QDs was assessed and compared using two approaches: power-modulated PL kinetics and fitting of PL amplitude saturation curves. Traditionally, the moderate excitation power interval was overlooked in the former approach due to the power dependence of average ACS values within this range. This study elucidates the reasons behind this power dependence and confirms the validity of ACS values at these excitation powers. We demonstrate that experimental conditions, specifically excitation pulse duration and power, can alter the distribution of decay parameters, leading to the power dependence of various average values, including decay lifetime and ACS. To illustrate this concept, we present a simple model with two contributing components, highlighting the major ideas. The key finding of this study is that both the low-power SD excitation and the moderate-power LD excitation form almost identical distributions of lifetime constants in an ensemble. These distributions exhibit a log-normal shape profile, unlike the Gaussian distributions observed with LD excitation at low excitation powers.

1. Introduction

Time-resolved (TR) photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy is a crucial, nondestructive technique for probing energy relaxation and transport kinetics in diverse systems. The most straightforward and common approach to analyze TR experimental data is the mono-exponential fitting. Many relaxation dynamic models and their subsequent implications assume that a decay process arising from HOMO-LUMO transitions is characterized by a specific lifetime constant, which is often valid. However, in practice, mono-exponential kinetics are rarely observed in experimentally measured PL from real samples, as these samples typically consist of an ensemble of emitters. Even if each emitter can be characterized by a single decay constant, inhomogeneity among emitters in the ensemble results in a distribution of decay constants.

For semiconductor quantum dots (QDs) capped with organic ligands, various factors contribute to this inhomogeneity, such as slight differences in size, shape, number of passivating ligand molecules, and their orientation. This continuous distribution of ensemble parameters makes the analysis and fundamental understanding of PL decay kinetics more intricate and nuanced than commonly assumed. Extracting lifetime distributions is generally challenging [1], so a common approach is to estimate a single lifetime representing the average or mean lifetime value of the ensemble. However, different types of averaging [2–4]

can result in diverse reported values in the literature, reflecting mathematical rather than physical differences.

This is just one aspect of the problem. A deeper issue is that the distribution of components can lead to fundamental, counter-intuitive consequences. For instance, it is commonly believed that decay lifetime does not depend on excitation power. This is true at relatively low excitation powers (linear excitation mode). In our previous research on silicon nanocrystals (Si NCs), we demonstrated [5] that in an ensemble with a lifetime distribution, the average decay lifetime becomes a function of excitation power in moderate excitation mode. In this study, we generalize this approach and show that e.g. the average absorption cross-section (ACS) can also be a function of excitation power.

Another traditional belief is that decay lifetime does not depend on the excitation pulse duration. This assumption holds for a mono-exponential profile but is not true for the average lifetime representing a distribution of components. Our previous studies [5–6] reported on two fundamental limits of sample excitation, namely short-duration (SD) pulse limit and long-duration (LD) pulse limit, where the average lifetime is independent of pulse duration. Here, we demonstrate that other parameters, such as ACS, can also depend on excitation pulse duration due to a distribution of partial ACS in the ensemble.

Among various experimental conditions, both excitation power and pulse length can alter component distributions in an ensemble. The ultimate challenge of this study is to verify whether varying these parameters can lead to similar distributions of components and, consequently, to matching average values of corresponding lifetimes or ACS. For demonstration purposes, we selected colloidal PbS QDs, which are ideal candidates owing to the strong confinement regime achieved in a few nm core due to the large exciton Bohr radius (18 nm). This allows us to focus on the size-dependent HOMO-LUMO optical transitions. Although PbS QDs suspension serves as a representative example, most conclusions in this study are applicable to a wide variety of emitter ensembles exhibiting non-monoexponential decay profiles.

2. Materials and methods

The oleic-acid (OA) capped core-type PbS QDs (QDot™ PbS-900-em) were purchased from Quantum Solutions, with a nominal mass concentration of 10 mg/ml in the stock solution. For experimental analysis, the PbS QD suspension was dispersed in toluene at a concentration of 6.25% relative to the stock solution and sealed into a quartz $0.5 \times 0.5 \text{ cm}^2$ cuvette with a volume of 0.75 ml.

Absorption and emission spectra of the sample are presented in Fig. 1. The absorption spectra were collected using a double-beam spectrophotometer (Specord 250, Analytik Jena). The absorption spectrum shows a distinct first excitonic peak with a maximum at approximately 746 nm. PL spectra were measured under 515 nm green solid-state laser (Cobolt Fandango 100) excitation using a home-made micro-spectroscopy setup with an imaging spectrometer (Hamamatsu C10027-02). The emission band closely resembles a Gaussian profile with a peak near 873 nm. The Stokes shift of about 127 nm is close to the nominal value (120 nm) reported by the QD producer.

Fig. 1. Absorbance (left axis, blue) and emission (right axis) spectra of PbS QD suspension in toluene. Solid dark yellow and dashed red curves represent PL emission spectra measured under 515 nm laser at different excitation powers. The dotted black curve represents a Gaussian fit of the PL spectra. Various dashed lines and arrows serve as guides.

Fig. S1 shows the variations of absorption and emission peaks as a function of QD mean size. Solid lines represent polynomial approximations of points obtained from figures presented in the "Technical data sheet: QDot™ PbS Quantum Dots." The green and brownish-red dashed lines, representing the absorption and emission optical peaks, were calculated according to equations delineated by Moreels et al. [7] and Reilly et al. [8], respectively. Notably, the solid and dashed lines closely match, with the dashed lines serving as asymptotes to the solid ones. Considering the absorption and emission peaks mentioned above, we estimated the mean QD core diameter to be approximately 2.6 nm, which is close to the nominal size of 2.7 nm provided by Quantum Solutions. Figure S3 presents an estimated particle size distribution based on the manufacturer's data, showing particle sizes ranging from approximately 2 to 3.3 nm (2.6 ± 0.7 nm).

Time-resolved decay transients were acquired using a commercial WITec alpha300R confocal Raman microscope modified for pulsed laser excitation and time-resolved single-photon detection. Excitation was performed using a 532 nm laser and an air objective (10x, NA = 0.25), where laser square pulses were formed by an acousto-optical modulator. The excitations with long and short pulses were conducted using 25 μ s long and 70 ns short pulses with corresponding duty cycles of 33% and 0.14%, respectively (Fig. 2). These excitation pulses effectively represent the LD and SD pulse limits, respectively, where the corresponding lifetime distributions of the particle ensemble are independent of pulse length [5–6]. The excitation radius and area were estimated to be approximately 1.3 μ m and 5.3 μ m², respectively. The PL signal was collected using the same objective, filtered through a 700 nm longpass filter, and detected with a single-photon counting avalanche photodiode (APD) with a rapid edge switching time faster than 50 ns. The experiment was driven using custom-written LabView software.

Fig. 2. Time-resolved normalized PL signals (PL amplitude is equal to 1) of PbS QD suspension, measured under LD (green curve) and SD (red curve) excitation at a power density of 9.56 W/cm². The onset and decay phases are indicated by dashed arrows.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 ACS determination with two approaches

A simple depopulation model considering a quasi-two level system was originally presented by Efros, Kovalev et al. [9–10], and slightly modified in our recent papers [11–12]. The model results in a system of three QD state-filling rate equations, which at low and moderate excitation powers ($I_{ex}\sigma \ll 1/\tau_A$) give the following dependence of the PL onset signal on a constant excitation I_{ex} [12]:

$$I_{PL}(t) = \frac{N_T I_{ex} \sigma \tau_{PL} / \tau_r}{1 + I_{ex} \sigma \tau_{PL}} \times [1 - e^{-(\frac{1}{\tau_{PL}} + I_{ex} \sigma)t}] = I_{PL}^{LD} [1 - e^{-(t/\tau_{ON})}] \quad (1)$$

where N_T is the total population of bright (luminescent) QDs, σ describes the cross-section for the absorption of photons, τ_{ON} , τ_{PL} , τ_r stand for the onset, PL decay, and radiative lifetimes, accordingly, I_{PL}^{LD} represents the PL amplitude at LD excitation. The onset lifetime characterizes the excitation (rising) part of TR PL signal curve, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The model assumes that the Auger recombination time τ_A is much shorter than τ_{PL} and τ_A is power-independent. Generally, there should be an additional term $I_{ex}^2 \sigma^2 \tau_A$ in the denominator [12], but in this range of excitation powers, we neglected it because it is still relatively low in comparison with $I_{ex} \sigma \tau_{PL}$.

From the above Eq. (1), we derive the formula for the PL amplitude:

$$I_{PL}^{LD}(I_{ex}) = \frac{N_T I_{ex} \sigma \tau_{PL} / \tau_r}{1 + I_{ex} \sigma \tau_{PL}} \quad (2)$$

and the interconnection between onset and decay lifetimes:

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{PL}} + I_{ex} \sigma = \frac{1}{\tau_{ON}} \quad (3)$$

Notably, these equations contain single values for both τ_{ON} and τ_{PL} , making them well-suited for single-exponential decay kinetics. However, decay kinetics from ensembles of emitters are almost never single-exponential. We can circumvent this by employing the mean values of the lifetimes.

The intensity-averaged $\bar{\tau}$ and amplitude-averaged $\langle \tau \rangle$ lifetimes can be calculated as follows [2]:

$$\bar{\tau} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N I_i (\tau_{PL}^i)^2}{\sum_{j=1}^N I_j \tau_{PL}^j}, \quad \langle \tau \rangle = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N I_i \cdot \tau_{PL}^i}{\sum_{j=1}^N I_j} \quad (4)$$

where I_i and τ_{PL}^i denote the amplitudes and lifetimes associated with the i^{th} component of the partial fit, respectively.

Physically, $\bar{\tau}$ represents the average lifetime during which the emitters remain in the excited state after the end of an excitation pulse, while $\langle \tau \rangle$ represents the mean value in the distribution of lifetime constants [2]. Finally, ACS of a sample can be estimated based on the modulation of PL lifetimes [Eq. (3)] or the PL amplitude [Eq. (2)] upon variation of the excitation power. We utilize both models and compare the results.

Fig. 3a (cyan diamonds) demonstrates variations of PL amplitude [see Eq. (1) and (2)] of spectrally integrated PL signal from PbS QDs in toluene as a function of LD excitation photon flux. When the excitation power is relatively low ($I_{ex} \sigma \ll 1/\tau_{PL}$), Eq. (2) simplifies to a linear function:

$$I_{PL}^{LD}(I_{ex}) = N_T I_{ex} \sigma \tau_{PL} / \tau_r \quad (5)$$

Fig. 3. (a) PL amplitudes under LD (cyan diamonds) and SD (pink diamonds) excitation are presented together with their fits (blue and brown curves) as functions of excitation photon flux, respectively. Black dashed curve serves as a guide of the linear part of discussed amplitude curves. (b) The extracted onset (red circles) and decay (black circles) lifetimes under LD excitation where the latter ones are calculated either as intensity-averaged (filled circles) or amplitude-averaged (opened circles). The extracted decay lifetimes under SD excitation are presented as blue squares. Low-excitation decay lifetimes under LD and SD excitations are highlighted with beige and orange stripes, respectively, while at moderate excitation the addressed lifetimes are expected to match at some point (yellow circle). (c) ACS as a function of excitation photon flux, calculated using intensity-averaged onset and decay lifetimes (represented by red and black circles in (b)). Dark red and violet stripes represent LD and SD excitation limits for ACS, accordingly. Various dashed and dashed-dotted lines are presented as eye-guides. Green, yellow and gray backgrounds highlight the low excitation, transition and moderate excitation modes, respectively.

If $I_{PL}^{LD}(I_{ex})$ is displayed in logarithmic scale, Eq. (5) indicates:

$$\log(I_{PL}^{LD}) = \log(N_T \sigma \tau_{PL} / \tau_r) + \log(I_{ex}) \quad (6)$$

Thus, $\log(I_{PL}^{LD})$ is not simply a linear function of $\log(I_{ex})$, but its slope should be exactly equal to 1 when I_{ex} is also displayed in log scale. Experimentally, $\log(I_{PL}^{LD})$ can sometimes demonstrate a linear dependence on $\log(I_{ex})$ even at very high excitation powers, but the slope in that case differs from 1. This simple check can verify whether in average a QD is yet excited with 1 photon when I_{ex} is not known in absolute values. The low excitation power range, where the dependence is still linear, is marked with the green region in Fig. 3. A blue triangle on the graph indicates that the slope is equal to 1, as per Eq. (6).

In the first approach, we calculated onset and decay lifetimes [Eq. (4)] during excitation power modulation. Experimental PL transients were treated using multi-exponential fits, with three exponentials providing high-quality fits:

$$I(t) = \sum_{i=1}^3 A_i \tau_i + offset \quad (7)$$

where the *offset* represents a constant noise level attributable to the detector's dark counts.

For details on uncertainty calculations in the fitting procedure, refer to [13]. The power dependence of the corresponding lifetimes is presented in Fig. 3b as red and black circles, respectively. These averaged lifetimes are utilized in the ACS calculation according to Eq. (3) as displayed in Fig. 3c (orange triangles). We consider three principal excitation power modes: (i) low excitation, (ii) transition, and (iii) moderate excitation, and discuss each mode in detail.

In the linear mode (green region), both lifetimes are power-independent and nearly equal to each other ($\tau_{ON} \approx \tau_{PL} \approx 1.75 \mu\text{s}$), following Eq. (3) under the assumption that $I_{ex} \sigma \ll \frac{1}{\tau_{PL}}$.

Therefore, this interval of excitation powers is unsuitable for ACS determination due a large error.

As the excitation power surpasses a certain threshold (Fig. 3, yellow stripe), the PL yield deviates from linear dependence. In this narrow transition mode, τ_{ON} shortens due to the non-negligible contribution of $I_{ex} \sigma$, while τ_{PL} remains constant. At these excitation powers, ACS can be reliably determined using Eq. (3). In our case, the obtained ACS value is approximately $1.2 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$, demonstrated in Fig. 3c with a red stripe. Considering that experimental τ_{PL} is on the order of 10^{-6} s , in the linear mode, the excitation photon flux should satisfy the condition $I_{ex} \ll 1/\sigma \tau_{PL} \approx 10^{22} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Consequently, it is well anticipated that the transition mode matches the interval $10^{20} - 10^{21} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

This method of determining the ACS offers an advantage over direct extraction from absorbance measurements because it does not require precise knowledge of particle concentration in the sample, which is often difficult to determine. A rough estimate of ACS, based on the optical absorbance at 400 nm and the equation for QD concentration in solution from Debellis et al. [14], yields a slightly overestimated value of $1.7 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$ (see SI for details). Considering the assumptions made, such as the omission of reflection and scattering effects, this value is reasonably consistent with the ACS value provided above.

In the moderate excitation mode, as indicated by the gray region in Fig. 3, the PL amplitude eventually saturates, aligning with the predictions from Eq. (2). During this mode, both the average onset and decay lifetimes decrease with increasing excitation power, as

depicted in Fig. 3b. This observation challenges the common, albeit erroneous, assumption in the literature on QD ensembles that average decay lifetime is power-independent. Recently we demonstrated [5] that this power dependence arises directly from the lifetime distribution of the constituent components within a QD ensemble. Eq. (1) is derived from a quasi-two-level system model, which assumes transitions occur at fixed rates. According to this model, the parameters should be power-independent. However, real QD ensembles almost always exhibit a distribution of lifetime components due to inherent inhomogeneities in the QDs (see e.g. Fig. S3). This distribution leads to non-exponential decay curves, necessitating an averaging of lifetimes in Eq. (1-3). Under these conditions, total and radiative decay lifetimes represented by average values remain constant upon changes in excitation power only in a linear and transition power modes, where the distribution of lifetime components remains unchanged.

As indicated in Fig. 3c, the ACS, calculated by Eq. (3) in the moderate excitation mode, also becomes a decreasing function of excitation power. This raises questions about the reliability of these values since they differ significantly from those obtained in the transition mode. In our previous publications [5,11], we noted that the model [Eq. (3)] is not valid in this mode. It should be remembered that Eq. (1) is based on the assumption $I_{ex}\sigma \ll 1/\tau_A$. The Auger lifetime of PbS QDs reported to be on the order of tens of picoseconds [15] which renders Eq. (3) applicable until $I_{ex} \ll 1/\sigma\tau_A \approx 10^{27} \text{ s}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$. Since the excitation photon fluxes considered in this study do not exceed $10^{25} \text{ s}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$, the term $I_{ex}^2\sigma^2\tau_A$ is still negligible relative to $I_{ex}\sigma\tau_{PL}$ and the validity of Eq. (3) remains well justified.

We will demonstrate that the observed decrease in ACS has a similar origin to the decrease in PL decay lifetime at higher excitation powers, and stems from a distribution of lifetime components within the QD ensemble. Although the ACS values observed are physical, in this power mode, ACS becomes dependent on excitation power as we show in the next section using a model with just two PL components.

In the second approach, we primarily focus on variations in PL amplitude, as illustrated in Fig. 3a. One might consider applying Eq. (2) to fit the PL amplitudes, thereby extracting the ACS as a fitting parameter. However, it should be noted that the average values of the involved parameters σ , τ_{PL} and τ_r are functions of the excitation power. Consequently, Eq. (2), strictly speaking, may no longer be valid under these conditions and should be regarded only as an approximate estimation. Furthermore, while experimentally obtained average values of $\tau_{PL}(I_{ex})$ can be utilized for fitting purposes, $\tau_r(I_{ex})$ are not directly ascertainable. A few assumptions can be considered here.

Under the assumption that the radiative rate remains constant – implying that variations of $\tau_{PL}(I_{ex})$ within the ensemble are solely attributable to non-radiative processes – the signal amplitudes can be simulated using the following model:

$$I_1^{sim}(I_{ex}) = \frac{AI_{ex}\sigma\tau_{PL}(I_{ex})}{1 + I_{ex}\sigma\tau_{PL}(I_{ex})} \quad (8)$$

where A is some constant in the model.

This assumption is particularly justifiable in cases involving a very narrow distribution of QDs, where all ensemble components arise from QDs of similar size. For instance, the estimated full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the PL spectrum is 190 meV (see Fig. 1), compared to the FWHM for a single PbS QD (i.e. homogenous linewidth related to excited state lifetime), which is reported [16] to be significantly broad (100±30 meV). This disparity suggests a substantial homogeneous contribution to the ensemble linewidth.

If the radiative rate substantially exceeds the non-radiative rate, i.e. $k_r = 1/\tau_r \gg 1/\tau_{nr} = k_{nr}$, then $\tau_{PL} \approx \tau_r$ and the signal amplitudes can be modeled using the following equation:

$$I_2^{sim}(I_{ex}) = \frac{AI_{ex}\sigma}{1 + I_{ex}\sigma\tau_{PL}(I_{ex})} \quad (9)$$

From separate experiments, we know that at a given concentration (6.25%), the external quantum yield (QY) of the studied sample does not surpass 20%. Assuming a rough equivalence between internal ($\eta = k_r/k_{PL}$) and external QY, one might estimate that $k_r \leq 0.2k_{PL}$ and the assumption $k_r \gg k_{nr}$ does not hold. Nonetheless, Eq. (9) remains valid under conditions where the internal QY is relatively homogeneous across the ensemble, which may be the case to some extent [17].

We applied Eq. (8) and (9) to fit the data (illustrated by the blue curve in Fig. 3a) and obtained ACS values to be approximately $1.2 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$ and $1.4 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$, respectively. This matches the ACS derived using the first approach surprisingly well, keeping into account the model assumptions and power dependence of its parameters.

3.2 Distribution of components as a function of excitation power

The perturbations observed in decay lifetimes and ACS in moderate excitation mode can be elegantly illustrated by simulating PL amplitudes (Fig. 4), where two decay components are considered: one short (1 μs , dark cyan) and one long (2 μs , orange). We simulate the PL amplitudes of these components using Eq. (2), assuming identical QY $\eta = \tau_{PL}/\tau_r = 1$ and number of bright QDs $N_r^S = N_r^L = 1$ for both. Two scenarios are considered: (i) the partial absorption cross-sections are equal $\sigma_s = \sigma_L = 1.2 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$, as shown in Fig. 4a and 4b, and (ii) the cross-sections are distinct, specifically $\sigma_s = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ cm}^2$ and $\sigma_L = 1.2 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$, as illustrated in Fig. 4c and 4d. The overall PL signal (black curve) represents the aggregate of these partial signals.

One can analyze the PL signal to observe the distribution of component amplitudes (inserts in Fig. 4a and 4c) under relatively low (10 W/cm^2 , shown as circles in Fig. 4) and high (1 MW/cm^2 , shown as squares in Fig. 4) excitation power densities. At lower excitation densities, both components operate in a linear mode, where the contribution of the short component is either equal to or less than that of the long component, depending on whether the absorption cross-sections are identical or varied (as seen in the circles in Fig. 4a and 4c inserts). Conversely, at higher excitation densities, a significant shift occurs where the short component's contribution surpasses that of the long component (as indicated by the squares in Fig. 4a and 4c inserts).

Why does the amplitude of the short component eventually dominate at higher excitation power densities? The perturbation begins when the excitation power density exceeds the linear mode threshold. Beyond this threshold, the amplitude of a component tends to approach its saturation limit, as described by Eq. (2), because the contribution from Auger recombination becomes significant. The key point is that this threshold differs between the short and long components. The long components apparently become saturated at lower excitation powers (see Fig. 4a and 4c) compared to the short components. This means that at a certain excitation power, when the amplitude of the long component has reached its saturation limit, the relative amplitude of the short component continues to grow with further increases in excitation power.

This phenomenon is fundamentally relevant to any ensemble of emitters with a distribution of lifetime components: modulation of excitation power in a non-linear mode alters the distribution of contributing components. Consequently, nearly all parameters defined in Eq. (1) become functions of excitation power. For instance, the variation in intensity-averaged lifetime, which is calculated using Eq. (4) and is modulated by excitation power, is depicted in Fig. 4b and 4d. This mirrors experimental observations (see Fig. 3b)

where the average decay lifetime decreases as a function of excitation power, primarily due to the increased contribution of the shorter component at higher excitation intensities.

Fig. 4 Simulated PL amplitudes (a, c) of short (S, dark cyan) and long (L, orange) components having corresponding partial decay lifetimes $\tau_s = 1\mu\text{s}$ and $\tau_L = 2\mu\text{s}$, along with average decay lifetimes (b, d), as a function of excitation power density under the assumptions that $\eta_s = \eta_L = 1$ and $N_r^s = N_r^L = 1$. The total PL amplitude, combining the short and long components (S + L, black curve), is shown with fits using Eq. (9) represented by a green dashed line. In (a) and (b), the partial ACS values are $1.2 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$. In (c) and (d), the partial ACS values differ, with $\sigma_s = 1.5 \times 10^{-17} \text{ cm}^2$ and $\sigma_L = 1.2 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$. Decay lifetimes are calculated as intensity-averaged (wine curve) or amplitude-averaged (dark yellow curve) using Eq. (4). Low-excitation limits for LD (dashed black line) and SD (dotted blue line) excitations, as well as the high-excitation limit for LD (dashed red line) and SD (dotted green line) excitations, are shown as guides. Low (circles in a, c) and moderate (squares in a, c) excitation power densities at 10 W/cm^2 and 1 MW/cm^2 are selected, with corresponding relative amplitudes displayed in the insets.

To estimate the ACS of an ensemble comprising two components, Eq. (9) can be employed to fit the PL amplitudes, illustrated by green dashed curves in Fig. 4a and 4c. As expected, when both components have equal ACS values, the ensemble ACS obtained from the fit approximates the partial ACS values $\sigma_{LD}^{fit} = 1.1 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$. When the partial ACS values differ, the estimated ensemble ACS from the fitting is approximately $\sigma_{LD}^{fit} = 6.1 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ cm}^2$, not significantly diverging from the average ACS at low excitation power: $\sigma_{av}^{LoP} = (N_s \sigma_s + N_L \sigma_L) / (N_s + N_L) = 6.75 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ cm}^2$.

Assuming original proportions such as e.g. $N_S = 1$, $\eta_S = 0.9$ and $N_L = 3$, $\eta_L = 0.2$, the estimated ACS from the PL amplitude fitting is $\sigma_{LD}^{fit} = 5.2 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ cm}^2$. Similarly to PL decay lifetime, this raises the question of how to determine an average ACS, as different averaging methods can be applied. One method involves summing the partial components at low excitation power (LoP), as described by Eq. (5):

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{PL}^{LoP}(I_{ex}) &= \sum_{i=1}^N N_i \eta_i \sigma_i I_{ex} = N_T \eta_{av} \langle \sigma_{LD}^{LoP} \rangle I_{ex} = \left(\sum_{l=1}^N N_l \right) \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N N_j \eta_j}{\sum_{l=1}^N N_l} \langle \sigma_{LD}^{LoP} \rangle I_{ex} = \\
 &= \left(\sum_{j=1}^N N_j \eta_j \right) \langle \sigma_{LD}^{LoP} \rangle I_{ex}
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

From this, the average value of ACS at low excitation powers can be derived using Eq. (10):

$$\langle \sigma_{LD}^{LoP} \rangle_B = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N B_i^{LD} \sigma_i}{\sum_{j=1}^N B_j^{LD}} \tag{11}$$

where partial amplitudes are given as $B_i^{LD} = N_i \eta_i$.

In the given scenario $\langle \sigma_{LD}^{LoP} \rangle_B = 5.7 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ cm}^2$ which is similar to $\sigma_{LD}^{fit} = 5.2 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ cm}^2$.

Therefore, in spite of the power dependence of parameters in Eq. (1) at moderate excitation power, the ACS values estimated using Eq. (9) are still a reasonable approximation of those obtained at low powers, as demonstrated previously.

In Eq. (11), we performed the ACS averaging using the part of the signal amplitude independent of ACS at low excitation powers. However, extending this averaging method to moderate excitation powers is not straightforward. Therefore, an alternative approach is to average ACS considering the total partial PL contribution I_i :

$$\langle \sigma_{LD}^{LoP} \rangle_I = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N I_i \sigma_i}{\sum_{j=1}^N I_j} \tag{12}$$

where I_i are defined by the general Eq. (2).

We employ this approach to illustrate the power dependence of ACS in the presence of a distribution of components with varying partial σ_i . Fig. 5 shows the simulated $\langle \sigma_{LD} \rangle_I$ for the last considered case where averaging was conducted over partial amplitudes modeled by Eq. (2). As shown, the PL signal-weighted ACS, similar to the decay lifetime, decreases as a function of excitation power in the non-linear regime until it stabilizes at a constant value. This decrease in ACS is solely attributed to the distribution of components with different partial ACS values.

Fig. 5 Simulated average ACS according to Eq. (12) for two partial components under varying excitation power density. The short and long partial components are modelled with the following parameters: $N_s=1$, $\eta_s=0.9$, $\tau_s=1\ \mu\text{s}$ and $N_L=3$, $\eta_L=0.2$, $\tau_L=2\ \mu\text{s}$. The dashed black and red lines represent ACS in low and high power limits, respectively.

In real samples containing PbS QDs, the short lifetime components are predominantly associated with small-sized particles that emit at the high-energy shoulder of the PL spectrum, as indicated by separate experiments involving spectrally resolved decay profiles (to be published in a separate study). Presumably, these small particles have significantly lower ACS compared to the mean value of the entire ensemble as has been demonstrated, e.g. for Si NCs [11]. Since the contribution of small particles with short lifetimes increases at high excitation powers, it is not surprising that under this excitation scenario, the mean ACS decreases significantly. It is important to note that in the opposite case – if the short components had higher ACS – the mean ACS value would increase upon raising the excitation power.

3.3 SD excitation vs high power LD excitation

So far, we have considered LD excitation under low excitation power. Let us now consider the high excitation power (HiP) limit in Eq. (2) when $1/\tau_{PL} \ll I_{ex}\sigma \ll 1/\tau_A$. In this case, the signal amplitude of the i^{th} component becomes independent of excitation power and ACS:

$$I_{LD,i}^{HiP} \approx \frac{N_i}{\tau_r^i} = \frac{N_i\eta_i}{\tau_{PL}^i} = \frac{C_i^{LD}}{\sigma_i\tau_{PL}^i} \quad (13)$$

where $C_i^{LD} = N_i\eta_i\sigma_i$.

Finally, we can estimate the PL signal-weighted average ACS under LD excitation at high excitation powers:

$$\langle \sigma_{LD}^{HiP} \rangle_1 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N I_{LD,i}^{HiP} \sigma_i}{\sum_{j=1}^N I_{LD,j}^{HiP}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N C_i^{LD}}{\sum_{j=1}^N \sigma_j \tau_{PL}^j} \quad (14)$$

In Fig. 5, the average ACS $\langle \sigma_{LD}^{HiP} \rangle$ calculated by Eq. (14) is presented by the red dashed line. In our previous studies [5–6], we demonstrated that in the SD excitation limit, when the pulse length $T \rightarrow 0$:

$$I_{SD,i} \approx I_{LD,i} \frac{T}{\tau_{PL}^i} \quad (15)$$

where $I_{SD,i}$ is the signal amplitude of the i^{th} component under SD excitation.

Considering a distribution of amplitudes $I_{LD,i}$ of partial components under long pulses, simply shortening the excitation pulse duration alters the distribution, resulting in different amplitudes $TI_{LD,i}/\tau_{PL}^i$ for the same partial components. In fact, in the short-pulse limit, partial amplitudes become weighted by their corresponding lifetimes, leading to a more pronounced relative contribution of fast components with short lifetimes compared to the long-pulse limit [5–6]. This effect is similar to the previously considered effect of high excitation power; therefore, we further directly compare them in terms of ACS and lifetimes.

Combining Eq. (12) and (15), we can derive:

$$\langle \sigma_{SD}^{LoP} \rangle_I = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N I_{SD,i} \sigma_i}{\sum_{j=1}^N I_{SD,j}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N C_i^{SD} \sigma_i}{\sum_{j=1}^N C_j^{SD}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{C_i^{LD}}{\tau_{PL}^i} \sigma_i}{\sum_{j=1}^N \frac{C_j^{LD}}{\tau_{PL}^j}} \quad (16)$$

From the comparison of Eq. (14) and (16), we conclude that, in the general case, the PL amplitude-weighted average ACS under LD excitation at high excitation powers $\langle \sigma_{LD}^{HiP} \rangle_I$ is different from the ACS under SD excitation at low excitation powers $\langle \sigma_{SD}^{LoP} \rangle_I$.

Above we have demonstrated that the average ACS values obtained from PL curve fitting σ_{fit} are close to $\langle \sigma^{LoP} \rangle_B$, but not $\langle \sigma^{LoP} \rangle_I$. Therefore, it is worth estimating $\langle \sigma_{SD}^{LoP} \rangle_B$:

$$\langle \sigma_{SD}^{LoP} \rangle_B = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N B_i^{SD} \sigma_i}{\sum_{j=1}^N B_j^{SD}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{C_i^{SD}}{\sigma_i} \sigma_i}{\sum_{j=1}^N \frac{C_j^{SD}}{\sigma_j}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{C_i^{LD}}{\tau_{PL}^i}}{\sum_{j=1}^N \frac{C_j^{LD}}{\tau_{PL}^j} \sigma_j} \quad (17)$$

Comparison between Eq. (14) and (17) reveals $\langle \sigma_{SD}^{LoP} \rangle_B = \langle \sigma_{LD}^{HiP} \rangle_I$, where for $\langle \sigma_{SD}^{LoP} \rangle_B$ the averaging was taken over ACS independent part of the total amplitude whereas in case of $\langle \sigma_{LD}^{HiP} \rangle_I$ the entire amplitude is ACS independent.

Fig. 3a demonstrates the variations in PL amplitude (pink diamonds) under excitation with 70 ns pulses (SD excitation). The calculated ACS values according to fittings with Eq. (8) and (9) are approximately $8.2 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ cm}^2$ and $9.2 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ cm}^2$, respectively. These values are indeed close to the ACS calculated from modulated lifetimes at high excitation powers (see Fig. 3c, violet stripe), indicating that $\sigma_{SD}^{fit} \approx \langle \sigma_{LD}^{HiP} \rangle$. In our previous study on Si NCs [5], we reported an ACS of $\sigma_{SD}^{fit} \approx 1 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$ for the solid sample, which again is very close to the ACS calculated from lifetime modulation under varied excitation powers.

A similar behavior is observed for the average decay lifetime. As previously reported, by combining Eq. (4) and (15), we derive:

$$\bar{\tau}_{SD} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N I_{SD,i} \cdot (\tau_{PL}^i)^2}{\sum_{j=1}^N I_{SD,j} \cdot \tau_{PL}^j} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N I_{LD,i} \cdot \tau_{PL}^i}{\sum_{j=1}^N I_{LD,j}} = \langle \tau_{LD} \rangle \quad (18)$$

where $\bar{\tau}_{SD}$ is the intensity-averaged lifetime under SD excitation and $\langle \tau_{LD} \rangle$ is the amplitude-averaged lifetime under LD excitation. Indeed, in the low excitation mode (Fig. 3b, green region), $\bar{\tau}_{SD}$ and $\langle \tau_{LD} \rangle$ are identical, presented as blue squares and open black circles, respectively. It is important to note that Eq. (18) is valid only in the linear and transition modes. In the moderate excitation mode (Fig. 3b, grey region), $\langle \tau_{LD} \rangle$ becomes significantly shorter, while $\bar{\tau}_{SD}$ remains almost power-independent. The nature of this discrepancy is not fully understood, and the correct applicability of the model should be restricted to the low excitation mode: $\bar{\tau}_{SD}^{LoP} = \langle \tau_{LD}^{LoP} \rangle$.

Both phenomena – (i) shortening of the excitation pulse length and (ii) increase of the excitation power in the non-linear regime – result in the shortening of decay lifetimes. As shown above, the former can be accounted for using Eq. (18). The latter can be calculated by combining Eq. (4) and (13) while considering that $I_{LD,i}^{LoP} = C_i^{LD} I_{ex}$ varies according to Eq. (5):

$$\bar{\tau}_{LD}^{HiP} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{C_i^{LD}}{\sigma_i} \cdot \tau_{PL}^i}{\sum_{j=1}^N \frac{C_j^{LD}}{\sigma_j}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{I_{LD,i}^{LoP}}{\sigma_i} \cdot \tau_{PL}^i}{\sum_{j=1}^N \frac{I_{LD,j}^{LoP}}{\sigma_j}} \quad (19)$$

It is worth modeling how variations in excitation power can result in a relative decrease of the intensity-averaged lifetime. In other words, how does $\Delta = (\bar{\tau}_{LD}^{LoP} - \bar{\tau}_{LD}^{HiP}) / \bar{\tau}_{LD}^{LoP}$ change as a function of partial components. To address this, we employ the aforementioned two-component model, selecting the long component as a reference and fixing its parameters: $\tau_L^{ref} = 2 \mu s$ and $\sigma_L^{ref} = 1.2 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$. Fig. 6 demonstrates the calculated Δ upon variations of the parameters of the short component, where $\bar{\tau}_{LD}^{LoP}$ and $\bar{\tau}_{LD}^{HiP}$ are calculated using Eq. (4) and (19), respectively. Evidently, Δ is equal to or close to zero when either the partial lifetimes or absorption cross-sections are identical. In the extreme case, when $\bar{\tau}_{LD}^{HiP}$ approaches zero, Δ approaches 1. This occurs when τ_s approaches zero, and there is at least a three orders of magnitude difference between the partial ACS values.

Fig. 6. Variations in the relative decrease of the intensity-averaged lifetime $\Delta = (\bar{\tau}_{cw}^{LP} - \bar{\tau}_{cw}^{HP}) / \bar{\tau}_{cw}^{LP}$ under modulated excitation power within the model, where the parameters of the reference long component are fixed ($\tau_L^{ref} = 2 \mu\text{s}$ and $\sigma_L^{ref} = 1.2 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$), while the lifetimes and ACS of the short component are varied.

From the comparison of Eq. (18) and (19), it follows that, in general, $\bar{\tau}_{SD}^{LoP} \neq \bar{\tau}_{LD}^{HiP}$. This can be well illustrated using the aforementioned two-component model. When the partial ACS values are equal $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2$, $\bar{\tau}_{SD}^{LoP} = \bar{\tau}_{LD}^{HiP} = \langle \tau_{LD}^{LoP} \rangle$, as shown in Fig. 4b. However, when σ_1 and σ_2 are different, $\bar{\tau}_{SD}^{LoP}$ and $\bar{\tau}_{LD}^{HiP}$ are also distinct (Fig. 4d).

In experiments, however, the equality between $\bar{\tau}_{SD}^{LoP}$ and $\bar{\tau}_{LD}^{HiP}$ is highly anticipated, as can be seen in Fig. 3b (orange stripe). At an excitation photon flux around $10^{25} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, these two average lifetimes are expected to match. A similar observation can be made for Si NCs in liquid suspensions [5]. One might suggest that the partial ACS values of components in the ensemble are not significantly different from each other. However, if that were the case, we would not observe the decrease in ACS upon increasing excitation power (Fig. 3c). Consequently, we postulate, based on accumulated experimental data, that in liquid samples the equality $\bar{\tau}_{SD}^{LoP} = \bar{\tau}_{LD}^{HiP} = \langle \tau_{LD}^{LoP} \rangle$ is highly expected. The original model [see Eq. (1)] is likely too simple to account for this behavior.

3.4 Modulation of lifetime distributions

So far, we have analyzed only the average lifetime values. However, examining the lifetime distributions provides even more insight. Fig. 7 presents the experimentally measured PL decay profiles of studied PbS QDs for three distinct cases: LD excitation at low power densities (on the order of W/cm^2) and high power densities (hundreds of kW/cm^2), as well as SD excitation at low power densities (tens of W/cm^2). It is evident that PL kinetics measured under LD excitation at low power densities are noticeably longer compared to the other cases. Conversely, PL kinetics corresponding to LD excitation at moderate power densities and SD excitation at low power densities are almost identical.

Fig. 7. Time-resolved experimental PL decay traces of PbS QD suspensions measured under LD or SD excitation at different excitation powers. The inset represents extracted lifetime distributions under LD (green colour) or SD (yellow colour) excitation at low power and LD excitation at high power (dashed lines). Two latter ones demonstrate a decent match.

The open-source MEMExp 6.0 code [18–19], which utilizes a hybrid Maximum Entropy Method with Non-Linear Least Squares (MEM/NLS) technique, was used to fit the experimental PL transients and extract unbiased distributions of decay components (inset in Fig. 7). The obtained distributions represent the inverse Laplace transform of the given PL decay profiles. Consequently, their behavior resembles the kinetics behavior described above. Thus, distribution profiles corresponding to LD excitation at low power densities are highlighted in green. These distributions are homogeneous and appear to closely follow a Gaussian profile. This distribution may mainly arise, for example, from a near-Gaussian distribution of particle sizes in the sample (see Fig. S3).

As discussed earlier, in the moderate excitation mode, the PL contribution of short components increases, and the lifetime distribution shifts towards shorter times (inset in Fig. 7, dashed lines). In this case, the distribution shapes resemble log-normal profiles. The distributions corresponding to SD excitation (inset in Fig. 7, yellow area) closely match these distributions. This suggests that not only average lifetimes but also lifetime distributions are similar when comparing SD with LD excitation at low and moderate excitation powers, respectively. This finding has practical implications, indicating that there is no need to pump a sample with large excitation powers to understand the sample's decay response.

4. Conclusions

This study elucidates the influence of excitation pulse duration and power on the PL decay profiles of emitter ensembles. We have demonstrated that these experimental conditions significantly affect the distribution of decay constants and, consequently, the average values of decay lifetimes and absorption cross-sections. This challenges traditional beliefs that these parameters are invariant under varying experimental conditions.

To fundamentally demonstrate this concept, we selected PbS QDs as a representative example and provided a simple theoretical model considering just two components. Specifically, we observed that in moderate excitation mode, both the average decay lifetime and ACS decrease with increasing excitation power. A similar behavior is observed upon modulation of the excitation pulse duration, transitioning from LD to SD excitation. These

variations are attributed to the inherent distribution of lifetimes and ACS within the QD ensemble.

The ACS of PbS QDs, about 2.6 nm in size, was assessed using two independent approaches that yielded close results: approximately $1.2 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$ under LD excitation and $(8.7 \pm 0.5) \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ cm}^2$ under SD excitation at low excitation powers. The latter value closely matches the estimated ACS under LD excitation at high excitation powers. Our findings indicate that low-power SD excitation can modulate the lifetime distribution similarly to moderate-power LD excitation, resulting in almost identical log-normal distributions of lifetime constants. This contrasts with the Gaussian distributions observed under low-power LD excitation. Consequently, the intensity-averaged lifetime of PbS QDs decreased from $\sim 1.75 \mu\text{s}$ under low-power LD excitation to $\sim 1.46 \mu\text{s}$ under moderate-power LD excitation or SD excitation. The similarity between lifetime distributions under low-power SD and moderate-power LD excitations offers a practical advantage, suggesting that detailed decay responses can be obtained without the need for high-power excitation.

By providing a comprehensive analysis of the modulation of lifetime distributions, this research underscores the importance of considering both excitation power and pulse duration in experimental setups to accurately interpret PL decay profiles and their implications for material characterization. It also generalizes the idea that any average parameter should be considered power-dependent when there is a distribution of partial lifetimes and components related to this parameter in an ensemble. These findings have broad applicability to various emitter ensembles, paving the way for more precise control and understanding of their behavior in diverse photonic applications.

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Data availability. Experimental raw data used in this study are available at [20].

Supplemental document. See [Supplement 1](#) for supporting content.

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